

M.-C. Dobrilă
Lecturer PhD, Faculty of Law,
“Alexandru Ioan Cuza” University of Iași, Romania

CONSIDERATIONS ON THE PRINCIPLES OF CONTRACTS AND THE
PRINCIPLES OF PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION OF THE GENERAL
DATA PROTECTION REGULATION (GDPR)

Rezumat. În articol sunt realizate corelații între principiile aplicabile contractelor, consacrate în dreptul contractelor, conform Codului civil român, și principiile din articolul 5 din Regulamentul General privind Protecția Datelor (GDPR). Articolul pune accent pe ideea că ambele categorii de principii urmăresc stabilirea unor repere pentru a orienta conduita părților implicate, fie în contracte pentru părțile contractante, fie pentru operatorii de date față de persoanele vizate. Articolul pune accent pe necesitatea de a asigura un echilibru între interesele părților contractante și protejarea bunei credințe în contracte, precum și pe necesitatea de a asigura protecția datelor cu caracter personal, cu cerințe legate de informare, transparență și responsabilitate.

Cuvinte cheie: contract, date personale, GDPR, bună-credință;

Abstract. The article draws correlations between the principles applicable to contracts, regulated in contract law, according to the Romanian Civil Code, and the principles in Article 5 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The article emphasizes the idea that both categories of principles aim to establish benchmarks to guide the conduct of the parties involved, either in contracts for the contracting parties or for data controllers towards the data subjects. The article emphasizes the need to ensure a balance between the interests of the contracting parties and the protection of good faith in contracts, as well as the need to ensure the protection of personal data, with requirements related to information, transparency and accountability.

Keywords: contract, personal data, GDPR, good faith.

Protection of personal data necessary for the conclusion and performance of contracts. Where personal data are processed for the conclusion and performance of contracts, there is a close link between the rules of contract law and the rules of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)¹. According to Article 4 of the GDPR, "personal data" are defined as "any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person" ("data subject"), and an identifiable natural person is defined as "one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an

¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0679-20160504> (03.05.2026);

online identifier or to one or more factors specific to his or her physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural or social identity".

Personal data may be lawfully processed under the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) only if there is a legal basis, in accordance with the legal grounds indicated in Article 6 or, in the case of special data (such as e.g. medical data, biometric data), in accordance with Article 9. According to Article 6(1)(a), the processing of personal data is lawful if the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes, in which case the basis for the processing of the data is the data subject's consent. According to Article 6(1)(b), the processing of personal data is lawful if "the processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract". There are also other legal grounds for processing data: legal obligation, vital interests of the data subject, performance of a task carried out in the public interest, legitimate interest. A clear distinction must be made between personal data that are necessary for the conclusion or performance of a contract, in which case the basis for processing will be Article 6(1)(b), and where personal data are processed for the conclusion or performance of a contract but are not necessary for the conclusion or performance of the contract or do not meet other conditions in Article 6(1)(b), in which case this legal basis for processing the data cannot be used; in this case, if the conditions are met, consent could be used as the legal basis for processing, even if it is for the conclusion or performance of a contract. The two legal bases for processing data should not be confused, nor is it permissible to use consent as the legal basis for processing simply because these data are processed in connection with a contract. Furthermore, the consent of the parties to conclude the contract, which is related to the agreement of will leading to the formation of the contract, should not be confused with the consent of the data subject to the processing of personal data.

If personal data are processed when concluding or executing contracts, in addition to the rules established in contract law, it is necessary to comply with the rules established in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which requires the establishment of correlations between the principles of contracts and the principles of the GDPR.

Considerations on the principles of contracts and the principles of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The principles regarding the processing of personal data are regulated in Article 5 of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), and the principles applicable to contracts are regulated in the Romanian Civil Code.

When personal data are processed in contracts, the principle of contractual freedom in Article 1.169 of the Civil Code (which stipulates that "the parties are free to conclude any contracts and to determine their content, within the limits imposed by law, public order and good morals") must be viewed in the light of the principles of the GDPR, which aim to protect the right to privacy and the fundamental right to

the protection of personal data¹; compliance with the requirements of the GDPR limits the contractual freedom of the parties, although compliance with the requirements of the GDPR is necessary to protect the data subject. Parties cannot invoke contractual freedom to justify the breach of their obligations under the GDPR.

According to the principle of lawfulness, fairness and transparency in Article 5(1)(a) of the GDPR, personal data must be processed lawfully, fairly and transparently in relation to the data subject. The data subject must be informed that his or her personal data are being processed, of the legal basis, of the purpose of the processing and must receive information about the data controller and the data protection officer.

The information must be concise, transparent, accessible and use clear and plain language. The requirement for the processing of personal data in a transparent manner is linked to the idea of fairness. With regard to the requirement for transparent processing, recital 29 of the GDPR states that any information about the processing of personal data must be easily accessible and understandable to the data subject and must use plain language².

Regarding the conclusion of contracts, information on data processing must be differentiated from other data, such as contractual data³.

The requirement to inform the data subject about the processing of his or her data is closely linked to the principle of accountability in Article 5(2) of the GDPR, according to which: the controller is responsible for complying with the requirements of the GDPR regarding the processing of personal data, he or she must take the necessary technical and organisational measures, and, in addition, must provide proof of compliance with them (for example, the concepts of "privacy by design" and "privacy by default", which means that data protection must be preventive and integrated from the design phase of the systems and by default). In addition, Article 5(1)(f) GDPR requires compliance with the principle of data integrity and confidentiality, which means that the controller must ensure the security of the data, in an appropriate manner, and take technical and organisational measures to protect it against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage.

The principles of personal data protection in the GDPR are closely linked to the idea of good faith of the data controller (although this principle is not expressly regulated in the GDPR), the purpose of the GDPR being to protect the data subject (right to privacy and right to protection of personal data) and to ensure that his or

¹ The right to the protection of personal data is regulated in Article 8(1) of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union and in Article 16(1) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union;

² The National Supervisory Authority for the Processing of Personal Data (ANSPDCP), Ghid întrebări și răspunsuri cu privire la aplicarea Regulamentului (UE) 2016/679, p. 19-21, <https://www.dataprotection.ro/servlet/ViewDocument?id=1650> (03.05.2026);

³ Article 29 Working Party - Guidelines on transparency under Regulation 2016/679, 29.11.2017, revised on 11.04.2018, p. 7, https://www.edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/article-29-working-party-guidelines-transparency-under-regulation_en (02.05.2026);

her rights are respected (right to information, right to erasure, right of access, right of opposition etc.).

If personal data is processed when concluding and performing a contract, a close connection is observed between the principle of legality, fairness and transparency and the principle of responsibility in the GDPR and the principle of good faith in civil law, regulated in Article 14 of the Romanian Civil Code, which refers to the fact that any natural or legal person must exercise their rights and perform their obligations in good faith, in accordance with public order and good morals (with the presumption of good faith, until proven otherwise).

Good faith in contracts means loyalty and honesty between the parties to the contract¹. Article 1170 of the Romanian Civil Code regulates the principle of good faith in contracts; the parties must act in good faith both when negotiating and concluding the contract and throughout its performance and cannot remove or limit this obligation, and Article 1183 of the Civil Code emphasizes the need to respect good faith in contractual negotiations.

According to the purpose limitation principle in Article 5(1)(b) of the GDPR, personal data must be “collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner incompatible with those purposes”; the data may be further used only if this is not incompatible with the initial purpose.

According to the data minimization principle in Article 5(1)(c) of the GDPR, the processed personal data must be “adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are processed”.

According to the principle of Article 5(1)(d) GDPR, processed personal data must be accurate and kept up to date, and all necessary steps must be taken to ensure that inaccurate data are erased or rectified without delay.

The principle of storage limitation, in Article 5(1)(e) GDPR, requires the data controller to keep the data “in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the data are processed”, and exceptionally, data may be stored for longer periods for archiving purposes in the public interest, statistical purposes or scientific research.

According to the principle of the binding force of the contract (*pacta sunt servanda*), regulated in Article 1.270(1) of the Civil Code, the contract produces binding effects for the parties and has the force of law for the contracting parties. According to the principle of irrevocability of the contract (*mutuus consensus, mutuus disensus*) in Article 1.270 paragraph 2 of the Civil Code, the contract is modified or terminated only by agreement of the parties or for reasons authorized by law. A close connection is observed between the principle of binding force (i.e. the principle of irrevocability) and the principles of the GDPR, because the binding force of the contract also extends to the obligation to comply with the rules of the GDPR. The contract is binding on the parties, but the binding force must take into account the requirements of the GDPR. The common point between the binding force of the contract and the principle of responsibility in the GDPR concerns an area

¹ Dimitrie Gherasim, *Buna credință în raporturile juridice civile*, Bucharest, Romanian Academy Publishing House, 1981;

with similar functions, because the data controller must also comply with the concluded contract and must also comply with the requirements of the GDPR. A connection can be observed between the irrevocability of the contract (which means that the parties' consent is required for the modification or termination of the contract) and the GDPR principles because the data controller cannot process the personal data of the person without their consent, and correct and transparent information of the person is also required in advance.

The principles of contracts concern the relationship between the contracting parties and aim to indicate the conduct of the contracting parties; the GDPR principles establish the requirements for how the data controller processes the personal data of the data subject, under conditions that ensure data security and confidentiality. There is a common direction for the principles of contracts and the principles of the GDPR, although in civil law there is an emphasis on contractual balance and under the GDPR the emphasis is on the protection of the personal data of the data subject.

Bibliography:

Article 29 Working Party - Guidelines on transparency under Regulation 2016/679, 29.11.2017, revised on 11.04.2018, p. 7, https://www.edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/our-documents/article-29-working-party-guidelines-transparency-under-regulation_en (02.05.2026);

Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, OJ C 202, 7.6.2016, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/treaty/char_2016/oj/eng (01.05.2026);

Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, OJ C 326, 26.10.2012, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A12012E%2FTXT> (01.05.2026);

Dimitrie Gherasim, Buna credință în raporturile juridice civile, Bucharest, Romanian Academy Publishing House, 1981;

Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation), <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/RO/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0679-20160504> (03.05.2026);

Romanian Civil Code, Law no. 287/2009. Official Gazette no. 505/2011;

The National Supervisory Authority for the Processing of Personal Data (ANSPDCP), Ghid întrebări și răspunsuri cu privire la aplicarea Regulamentului (UE) 2016/679, <https://www.dataprotection.ro/servlet/ViewDocument?id=1650> (03.05.2026).

